

W. K. Burns
Code 5671
Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, DC 20375
202-767-4928
fax 202-767-0966

Summary

Recent progress in the development of velocity matched broadband LiNbO₃ modulators has opened new opportunities for the demonstration of low drive voltage devices at specific frequencies. This paper will review the current status of device development and illustrate the design of low drive voltage devices.

Velocity matched traveling wave devices in LiNbO₃ require the reduction of the microwave phase velocity so that it equals the optical phase velocity. Generally this is done by manipulating the geometric structure and layer thicknesses of the electrodes and buffer layers making up the coplanar electrode structure. Early velocity matched devices(1-3) tended to achieve velocity matching at the expense of impedance matching which in turn resulted in some degradation in performance. The difficulty in achieving simultaneous velocity and impedance matching arises from the high dielectric constant of LiNbO₃(~35). Progress in overcoming this problem has come from two developments: First, the use of ridge waveguide structures(4) which use physical etching to remove the high dielectric constant LiNbO₃ material, and thus add an additional degree of freedom in the design problem. Second, the realization that increasing the electrode gaps can actually improve device performance even though the field across the waveguides is reduced(5,6). This occurs because the improvement in electrode loss at the larger gap gives a larger benefit than the negative effect of the simultaneous increase in voltage-length product. These

U.S. Government Work Not Protected by U.S. Copyright

improvements have allowed the demonstration of simultaneous velocity and impedance matched devices with very large (>100 GHz) bandwidths(7). As there is an inherent trade-off between bandwidth and drive voltage in the design of these devices one can exploit these approaches to obtain lower drive voltages in devices with limited bandwidth.

Fig.1 shows a device cross-section with etched regions between the electrode gaps. Finite element calculations have been carried out to determine microwave loss coefficient, electrode thickness(t_g), and ridge height(t_r), as a function of electrode gap(W)(Fig.2), for velocity and impedance matched devices. By calculating the overlap integral for the resulting electrical fields and measured optical mode profiles, the voltage-length product vs. gap width can be obtained as shown in Fig.3. These results can be used to design devices with specified drive voltages at a given frequency. We will explore the use of these techniques to achieve designs for low drive voltages at defined frequencies in limited bandwidth devices.

1. M. Seino, N. Mekada, T. Yamane, Y. Kubota, and M. Doi, Tech. Dig. ECOC'90, paper ThG1-5(1990).
2. G. K. Gopalakrishnan, C. H. Bulmer, W. K. Burns, R. W. McElhanon, and A. S. Greenblatt, Electron. Lett. 28, 826(1992).
3. D. W. Dolfi and T. R. Ranganath, Electron. Lett. 28, 1197(1992).
4. K. Noguchi, O. Mitomi, H. Miyazawa, and S. Seki, J. Lightwave Tech. 13, 1164, 1995.
5. O. Mitomi, K. Noguchi, and H. Miyazawa, Tech. Dig. LEOS'95, paper IO4.1(1995).
6. R. Madabhushi, Tech. Dig. OFC'96, paper ThB3(1996).
7. K. Noguchi, O. Mitomi, and H. Miyazawa, Tech. Dig. OFC'96, paper ThB2(1996).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3